

The Effectiveness in Personnel's Performance Development in The Road Freight Carrier Business

Akkarat Poolkrajang, Sakarin Yuphong

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Abstract

This research aims to develop personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business a trainer skill. The effective trainer helps personnel increasing operational performance in the road freight carrier business. The monitoring and evaluating personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business have been followed. The samples used in training are personnel in the road freight carrier business. They are 20 department leaders consists of establishment executives who send employees to participate in personnel development. In addition, there are at least 180 employees who attained the 6 training courses which each program duration is spending at least 3 days. After training, the researchers monitor and evaluate personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business of 540 employees in the organizations including colleagues, subordinates, customers or service providers, and trainees. The statistical analysis of data is conducted to find the course performance and course effectiveness index. The responding rate on questionnaire after training is 80.10 percent. Satisfaction rate is 84 percent. The training location is considered the most rating. The participators give the opinion of satisfaction on the practical of training course which they can relate the training topics with their work and can benefit their current works. For the 360 degrees of the performance evaluation method, result of satisfaction and opinion are ranks the most among others.

Introduction

In business, there is a clear link between the storage and transport. In order to minimize transport, the number of deliveries should be increased, which in turn entails the need to increase the number of means of transport. To make transport fulfill its task properly, the process of transportation should be fast, flexible and precise. Because of the cost, it is necessary to keep an eye on the means of transport, make sure that are they best loaded and avoid any kind of empty trips, which generate entirely unnecessary costs. All of these activities for individual companies can be extremely difficult, time consuming and costly, and above all require certain specific conditions, such as having a huge warehouse, when company is unable to have it. The logistics centers, having adequate storage space and the number of transportation modes, are able to meet all logistical tasks - from supply logistics to the logistics of distribution. (Department of International Trade Negotiations, 2016).

The impact of the Free Trade Agreement (FTA), the significant trade liberalization agreement and the impact on logistics services business are very important and have an impact to Thai economics. Especially, the direct impact of ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) in relation to the framework for other free trade zones negotiations. Thai logistics is affected by trade liberalization. Thailand is inevitably affected by the logistics services including land, air and sea freight services. For example, road transport service, rail transport, air freight services, parcel delivery and non-shipping services include sea freight services, warehouse services, shipping agent service as well as customs clearance service, etc. (Office of the National Economic and Social Development Board (Pat Council) (2016), World Bank Group US. (2016)

The transportation is not only the most important in logistics processes but also the key logistic activity is transportation. Thus, the transportation cost is often the main cost of the entire logistics process which is approximately 40 percent of total cost. Transportation flows goods which are considered services of resources within the supply chain. The effectiveness of handling in transportation service is a critical element to reduce logistics costs as well as the resulting in efficiency in the logistics process. Moreover, the quality transportation management must be translated in terms of the punctual delivery. The condition of intact goods and complete shipping will result in better customer service, which will result in better business development. Although, transportation activities are not incurred directly to create value added to goods and services, but it is essential

part of the support activities that enhance the successfulness of the business transaction to customers. The Ministry of Industrial Economics, Ministry of Industry (2017)

In the era of borderless society, the understanding and knowledgeable human resources will give the investor more confidence in the growing and sustainability of the road freight carrier business group. In addition, the global trade liberalization helps improving competition for new services, increase service efficiency, and enable entrepreneurs and the general public to convey their knowledge of management. Therefore, the development of personnel to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business is crucial. New technologies in the road freight service business for personnel will create opportunities in learning the company will be able to develop the road freight service provider business as well as to increase the competitiveness for Thailand.

Objectives

- To develop the trainer in human resource development and to increase operational competency in the road freight service business
- To develop personnel and to increase work competency in the road freight carrier business
- To monitor and to evaluate human resource development in order to increase operational competency in the road freight service business

Method

In the research of human resource development to increase work competency in the road freight service providers, the researcher uses research methods in the form of research and development methodology as follows

Population and samples

There are two types of samples which are related to train the trainers and professional development courses. First, train the trainer Samples are lecturers who participate in personnel development courses to increase operational performance in the road freight service business. They are 20 establishment executives and supervisors. Researcher applies the selecting purposive sampling by qualifications to have experience at least 5 years in related to road freight business. Second, professional development samples are the group of employees who participate in develop personnel courses to increase work competency in the road freight carrier business.

The development personnel must work in the transportation and distribution business and affiliated with professional associations such as the Land Transport Association of Thailand and Thai Shipping and Logistics Association and Import and Export Shipping Association. There are at least 180 people selected by using the purposive sampling. The qualifications are consistent with the related curriculum at each level of the profession.

The total of 540 samples which are tracked and evaluated personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business. Samples consist of establishment executives who send employees to participate in personnel development and Colleagues, subordinates, customers or service providers, and trainees. Purposive Sampling qualifications are consistent with the curriculum at each level of the profession and must have a relationship with the trainee.

Research Operations

To develop training courses to be a lecturer in personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business. Train the Trainers are conducted for 40 hours with 20 trainees. In order to develop personnel to increase operational competency in the road freight service business by conducting training courses developed for 180 employees by using the above key speakers.

To monitor and evaluate personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business. Researcher applies the Kirkpatrick's theoretical concept of RLBR which consists of 4 aspects which are reaction assessment (Reaction), learning assessment (Learning), evaluation of behavior changes (Behavior) and evaluation of results (Results).

Research Tools

Research tools to develop personnel to improve operational performance in the road freight carrier business are as follows:

Train the trainers consist of training course in the development of personnel to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business .The 40-hour period consists of theoretical content about business performance techniques in the road freight carrier business .Transfer techniques and theoretical teaching practices and teaching practices

Course to develop for personnel to increase work competency in the road freight service business, consisting of 6 courses, divided by levels as follows:

Courses Levels	Training Courses
Beginning	1 .Receiving and delivering goods from road freight 2 .Basic Road freight handling
Intermediate	3 .Techniques and methods of vehicle control in road freight 4 .Guidelines for preventing and resolving road freight accidents
Advance	5 .Road freight planning and control 6 .Road freight business management

The knowledge test is used in 4 multiple choices which are validated by 5 experts .The validations include the correctness of contents and the precision of language .The evaluation is covered all the areas of research objectives .The results showed that the Index of Item-Objective Congruence (IOC) Tuntavanitch, P. and Jindasri, P. (2018) test was between 0.80-1.00 and the confidence of the test, which was conducted by the Alpha coefficient .The confidence of the knowledge test during training was 0.96 and the confidence of the post-training knowledge test confidence at 0.92.

Follow-up form and evaluation of personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business .Kirkpatrick's theoretical concept (RLBR) (Kirkpatrick, Donald L:1994) consists of 4 aspects 1) reaction assessment (Reaction2),3)Behavior assessment and 4)Assessment of results .The IOC analysis found that the IOC value was between 0.80-1.00 and the confidence value, finding the Alpha coefficient. By the reliability of the opinion evaluation form confidence level at 0.97.

Data Collection

Collecting data from trainers of both trainthe trainerscourses and the develop personnelto increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business courses in the total of 6 courses who passed the knowledge, practice and behavior tests throughout the course. Collecting data from monitoring and evaluating personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business .With a queryresearcher coordinate with the shipping and distribution business establishments to clarify the purpose of the research and provide self-questionnaires together with online questionnaires and e-mails to businesses .A total of 540questionnaires were received and collected (100 percent).

Data Analysis

Researcher used data analysis bycontent analysisfor course development and used a statisticalprogram to analyze quantitative data for average and standard deviation .

Research Results

The result of the development of speakers in human resource development to increase operational competency in the road freight service business.

Training Assessment Results

1)Theoretical assessment results of training courses for lecturers 'participants were found to take a post-training test with a score of 50, with the participants achieving an overall average score of 40.05 which considers 80 percent .

- 2) Evaluation of teaching practices training courses for lecturers which found that participants with a full score of 100 were able to achieve an overall average score of 84 percent.

Satisfaction Assessment Results

- 1) General information of 20 participants which consist of 15 males and 5 females .The business owners are considering of 75% male and 25% female owners which concludes business owners of 40%, managers of 30%, department head 15% and 15% employees.
- 2) Satisfaction in training courses, mainly in terms of the appropriateness of the course location yield the highest score which average 4.89.
- 3) In terms of training, we found that the participants were satisfied with the training, most of whom were satisfied in the field of being able to apply the knowledge they received to the highest score of application benefits which average 4.89.

The results of human resource development to increase work competency in the road freight carrier business

- 1) Total number of participants 180 participants with 6 courses. Each course has a training period of not less than 3 days.
- 2) Training methods by level and course include :Lecture and action training in all 6 courses .Especially, courses 5 and 6 include site visit which allow training executives to see up-to-date technology and able to apply information to their own companies later.
- 3) Course performance evaluation results by using formula which are process (E1), result (E2), and activity or practice (E3). All courses are served effectively according to the criteria set of 80/80/80 .The effectiveness of learning analyzes by using the Effectiveness Index (E.I.) (Goodman, R.I. :1980) The results of every course's evaluation have a effectiveness index greater than 0.50, indicating that all courses have increased learning outcomes, which are consistent with the efficiency which follows Merguigans ratio (Monchai Thientong : 2011).which yield more than 1.00 in all courses, meaning that all courses are effective in accordance with the criteria set and applied to training well.
- 4) The results of the training participant satisfaction assessment show that the participants were satisfied with the high level of course, namely 1 .Receiving and delivering goods from road freight and 6 courses of road freight business management, the remaining 4 courses are 2. Basic road transport management .3 .Techniques and methods of vehicle control in road freight transportation. 4 .Guidelines for preventing and resolving road freight accidents and 5 .The participants were most satisfied with the level of the course.

In summary, the results of personnel training in Thailand's logistics business have been developed for 180 professional performances, with the training of the participants at least 80 % achieved. The number of entrepreneurs participating in the project is at least 80 percent .Entrepreneurs are satisfied with the performance of the trainers at a very satisfied level .Results of monitoring and evaluation, personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business .By evaluating the opinions in a 360-degree format, the course participations consist of supervisors and employees as well as business partners in a total of 540 cases, assessments on each side of the assessors found that

- 1) Participants have a high level of feedback on all aspects, which is worth the feedback on this training course .The lecturer has the technique of lectures .Use of appropriate media and transfer knowledge in a clear and clear order .Gain knowledge and experience after participating in the program and have the knowledge gained from the training to disseminate or exchange learning between colleagues.
- 2) Supervisors have a higher level of feedback on all aspects, which is worth the feedback about this training course .Training courses respond to the needs of the agency's personnel development and promote the progress of the personnel .Personnel have changed their performance behavior, resulting in efficient work .And personnel in the agency apply knowledge conveyed by the developers to perform their tasks such as lecturers, presentations and training materials, etc. These yield the highest feedback.

- 3)Subordinates give a high level of opinion in all aspects, which is more knowledgeable about the operation and can bring the knowledge gained from training to subordinates regularly. These yield the highest feedback.
- 4)Colleagues have a high level of opinion in all aspects, which opinions about participants are required to take part in human resource development programs in the transportation provider business to increase competitiveness. Trainees participated in the Human Resource Development Program in the transportation provider business to increase their competitiveness on time. Trained people have increased confidence in their operations and the operations in the agency have the correct standard of work. These yield the highest feedback.
- 5)Customers or clients have also a high level of opinions in all aspects which opinions about helping when problems occur, the highest opinion level.

Summary and Discussion

The researcher has been developed a prototype training program kit for human resource development to increase the competitiveness of the shipping and logistics services business. Based on professional logistics standards, it prepares for the liberalization of the ASEAN Community and creates economic value for the country sustainably. Train the Trainers in this research project has been developed by a trainer selected by experts in the transport profession. The coaching technique is used to provide coaching performance to be used as a train the trainers for a number of truck drivers at least 180 cases. The project has been developed to increase its potential according to the program at both the operating level, the supervisor level and the executive and owner level. To achieve the objectives of this project, which has the success of learning from this project in accordance with the project's goals.

The benefits are not only to help the development of human resources in the transportation provider business under this program. It also helps to lay the groundwork for these trainers in expanding their results as trainers who build human resources in both their own and the drivers of the transportation profession after the project ends. This will help to improve the competitiveness of human resources in the country's transportation provider business. In addition, the follow-up and evaluation of the training is not less than 30 days. RLBR by evaluating the opinion in a 360-degree format, consisting of trainees, Commander Colleague Subordinate Business partners or service recipients a total of 540 cases. The response evaluation learning behavioral change and the results to the organization, which found that the evaluation results in all aspects are at a good.

Discussion of the findings

Development of lecturers in personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business regarding to the theoretical assessment of training courses for preparing to be trainers. The results of the teaching practice assessment, the participants took a post-training test for the overall average score of 80.10%. Training courses for lecturers It found that trainees were able to achieve an overall average score of 84.00%, which was quite high. The satisfaction assessment in training and training program management which most of them are satisfied with the suitability of the project location at the highest level. As the researchers designed the lecturer training courses at each level in accordance with the course development process, and the researchers used the principle of analysis of the subject, which resulted in the training content being quite detailed and in the training course which took 5 days. The content is divided into two areas: theoretical and practical aspects, resulting in a very good level of lecturer training in line with the visual aspects Khemthong and Ngamvichaikit (2018) study on the assessment of knowledge, skills and utilization in the small hotel. They find that training session showed that the participants are able to assessed their knowledges and skills. The training courses are useful at the highest level.

Personnel development to increase operational performance in the road freight carrier business. The results of the course performance evaluation with the formula using the formula $E1 / (results) E2 / (activities or practical tasks) E3$. (All courses are effective according to the criteria set 80/80/80 and analysis of the effectiveness of learning using the learning effectiveness index value. The results of all courses have an effectiveness index higher than 0.50 as all courses have increased learning outcomes, in line with the results of the Merguigans ratio performance analysis. The results of the training experience showed that the participants were satisfied with the highest level of course satisfaction. The 4 courses include basic road freight management course, techniques and methods of vehicle control in road freight transport course, course on how to prevent and solve road accident accidents, and lastly, road freight planning and control course. As the researchers developed a course in

according to professional standards in the field of freight management, which meets real operational performance. The integrated knowledge and skills from practical operations to provide training to personnel in the road freight carrier business, and trainees who worked in road freight companies. The research results in the professional development of six professional course which evaluated at a higher level than the specified criteria. Boonsong and Kulwachirawan (2018) study the assessment of training courses effectiveness. Their aim is to develop the 4 main operational staff skills. Professional support group finds that more than 70% of the training period stipulated by their researchers are satisfied with passing grade. The average score is 76.22 points above the set threshold. In addition, staffs are highly satisfying with the training courses. Partner or Service Provider Each aspect of the assessment was assessed that the trainee had a high level of feedback in all aspects due to the fact that after the trainees had passed the training and returned to work in the facility. The results of the operation are more accurate. A better understanding of practical work. As a result, the efficiency of the operation surges, which the management of the establishment and the service providers or customers see the benefit of the development of employees to enhance their work. It represents the confidence of the establishment to be able to provide services effectively. As a result, the overall assessment is very high, which is in line with Asrangkoon (2016). Research on professional training assessments for women found that the overall professional training assessment was very appropriate. In terms of the use of knowledge that has been used for family/lifestyle use as well as bringing knowledge to core and complementary occupations which consequently the revenue increases.

Recommendations

From this research study, the train the trainers project should be expanded. There are personnel that need this train the trainer project in both Thai transport and logistics business, both supervisors and potential entrepreneurs with knowledge and skills in operation and management, as well as a good attitude to the service sector. The Teaching, coaching, knowledge transfer, learning resource management, media design and development, etc. If such personnel are brought in to enhance their skills to become the professional trainers, the new trainers are also considered a human resource that helps to create sustainability in Thailand's transportation and logistics business.

Human resources development projects should be expanded in the transportation and logistics businesses more broadly because the sample in this research is limited to 180 cases. However, the expansion should be considered to cover various dimensions. In addition to the number, such as regional dimensions (all 4 regions in Thailand) as well as the enterprise size dimensions (to cover small -medium-large enterprises).

The curriculum should be developed both to expand and extend from the original, such as expanding the effect to cover other modes of transport (waterways, air, rail, pipelines). It should be considered in the dimensions of the number of people and operators that are present. The course content should be more competence-oriented than academically with an institution already in operation. The course should be based on professional standards and professional qualifications as well as all courses in this program to ensure the scope of the content in line with professional standards. The develop transportation and logistics courses in other dimensions, such as energy-saving safety courses in the transportation sector. Courses in the field of transportation of hazardous materials, etc.

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Author Information

AkkaratPoolkrajang

Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi
39 Moo1, Klong 6 Khlong Luang Pathum Thani
12110, Thailand

SakarinYuphong

King Mongkut’s University of Technology North
Bangkok
Address of Institution or University
1518 Pracharat 1 Road,Wongsawang, Bangsue,
Bangkok 10800 Thailand
